

An analysis of the influence of emissivity in the heat transfer for constructive details of composite insulated panels with metallic skin under summer and winter conditions

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Summary: Under the assumption that first is necessarily a comprehensive study in order to optimise, this paper has the purpose to evaluate the energy performance for a range of usual constructive details of composite insulated panels with metallic skin through steady-state FEM analysis, for both summer and winter conditions, and also to make an analysis of the influence in the thermal bridges that occurs of the variation of emissivity in time, specific for galvanized steel.

Keywords: steady state heat flux transfer; insulated sandwich panels; numerical analysis; energy performance; buildings.

1. Introduction

The interest for the energy efficiency of the buildings has enhanced in the last years at large scale, due to the high rise of global CO₂ emissions. Although, especially for residential buildings and for usually constructive solutions as masonry or reinforced concrete, there are many detailed studies regarding the heat flux transfer under certain conditions and their impact on the energy demand and consumption of the building (Asava and Rusu, 2017; Kotti et. al. 2017), there are relative new technical envelope solutions for which thermotechnical scientific studies are limited (Măgurean et. al. 2014). More than that, usually the values of the linear thermal coefficients are determined numerically and analytically under winter conditions, but not under summer conditions and also, specific material properties that are known to change over time during the operation of the building, usually is not taken into consideration.

2. Materials/Methods

FEM steady-state numerical analysis is undertaken, in accordance with ASRO (2017) prescriptions, with the purpose to study the influence of summer and winter conditions on the heat flux transfer for several constructive details specific to thermal insulated sandwich panels. To compare the effect of the two different sets of boundary conditions, the results of the numerical analysis are integrated in analytical calculation in order to determine the linear transfer coefficients values, which are regularly used by the building energy auditors in heat losses calculation, in order to determine the energy demand and energy consumption of the building.

Both of the studies are also performed for different values of the emissivity, which is variable in time for galvanized steel, as can be noticed in the report undertaken by EC (2014), in order to determine the influence of this particular material property on the different thermal bridges that occurs in the constructive details. The emissivity influences the heat transfer through radiation at the surface of the constructive element. As regarding the variation of emissivity, for this study were used values of $e = 0.28$ and $e = 0.9$, provided in EC (2014).

The studied details include some of the most important constructive details of the building: walls and roof, the interaction between them, the interaction between window and wall (see Figure 1), with a comprehensive model for the air cavities of the window frame and glass, and the interaction between wall and ground (see Figure 2), also with a comprehensive model for the slightly ventilated grooves with small cross section which are constructively specific for the wall panel's joint with the slab on ground.

Figure 1: Geometrical detail of wall-to-window connection

Figure 2: Geometrical detail of wall panel joint with slab on ground

3. Results and Discussion

For the constructive detail of wall-to-window connection, the temperature field distribution is presented as isothermal maps shown in Figure 3. The numerically obtained results are centralised in Table 1, for 4 distinct cases of analysis.

Figure 3: Isothermal surfaces for analysed cases with $e = 0.9$ (a) winter conditions - left (b) summer conditions - right

Table 1. Thermotechnical performance of wall panel into wall-to-window connection constructive detail

Condition type	Thickness [mm]	e [-]	T_i [°C]	T_e [°C]	R_{wall} [m ² K/W]	Ψ_{wall} [W/(mK)]
Winter	120	0.28	20	-18	3.449	0.136
	120	0.9	20	-18	3.325	0.169
Summer	120	0.28	25	33	3.499	0.118
	120	0.9	25	33	3.357	0.151

Regarding winter and summer conditions, it can be concluded that the effect of the thermal bridges is reduced under summer conditions, noticed as general effect. Further, it can be observed that the value of emissivity has a significant impact in the thermal performance of wall panel, with 19.53 % reduction in ψ -value (linear thermal transfer coefficient), for winter conditions, and 21.85 % for summer conditions, for results obtained with $e = 0.28$ vs. $e = 0.9$.

The great diversity of the existing constructive details using insulated sandwich panels makes it impossible to have a complete analysis of these types of envelope solutions, but the results of numerical simulations of current constructive details provide an insight into the influence of geometric and / or material linear thermal bridges. Though, the current results offer a comprehensive knowledge about the energy performance of the analysed details, with a focus on the specific characteristics of the used surface material and their effect in the thermal analysis.

4. Conclusions

This comprehensive approach of the topic is made in order to understand the thermal response under different boundary conditions for composite insulated panels with metallic skin.

The results of ψ -values can be used as working data for energy auditors and building designers, in order to obtain accurate information regarding the energy consumption of a range of non-residential buildings such as: conditioned industrial halls, office buildings, commercial buildings, etc., that currently are using this type of building envelope solution.

5. References

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